

A Study of Analysis of Reasons for Pre - Donation Deferrals Among Whole Blood Donors at A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in North Karnataka – An Institutional Experience

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Abstract

Background: The safety of blood donors forms a crucial component for safe blood transfusion services. The policies that govern donor eligibility form an integral part of blood safety which is designed to ensure selection of healthy donors and also to protect recipients. Donor deferral as a result of risk factors is a standard practice worldwide.

Objective: The aim of our study is to analyse the different reasons of blood donor deferrals. Donors who are deferred generally have negative attitude towards blood donation process and in future, these donors are less likely to return for donation. Retention of the temporarily deferred donors can be achieved to a great extent by analysing the various reasons for deferrals and eliminating the causes wherever possible.

Methods: This was a single-centre, retrospective study which was conducted at the blood bank of a tertiary care teaching hospital in North Karnataka from 1st January 2022 to 30th November 2024. It involved donors who donated blood at the blood bank as well as at outdoor blood donation camps. These donors were evaluated by the medical officer in - charge and were deferred during different stages of evaluation (Stage 1- History taking, Stage 2- Physical examination and Stage 3- Haemoglobin estimation). Individuals who did not fulfil the criteria for donation were deferred with reason being documented in the deferral register, from which data was retrieved for study.

Results: In our study, 344 (8.92%) of donors were deferred from blood donation of the total 3855 blood donors. Most of the deferrals were temporary while few were permanent. Majority of the deferred donors were in the age of 18 – 30 years. Deferral rate was high among females compared to males. High blood pressure among potential donors was the most common cause for temporary deferral whereas donors who are diagnosed with diabetes on medication was the most common cause for permanent deferral.

Conclusion: Temporarily deferred donors were higher than permanently deferred donors. Most studies indicate high percentage of donor deferrals due to temporary reasons. Identifying the reasons and frequency of donor deferral aids in preventing loss of precious blood units by helping to retain the donor pool.

Keywords: Blood donation, Temporary Deferral, Permanent Deferral, Anaemia

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Introduction

A crucial procedure in the current medical practice is Blood Transfusion, owing to its life - saving ability in many instances as road accidents, surgical procedures, post - partum haemorrhage, anaemia, etc [1]. Its reported that around 11 million blood donations happen in India every year which is against the requirement of 13.5 million in our country. The statistics from World Health Organisation (WHO) depict that, annually more than 81 million blood units are collected, but the contribution from developing nations is only 39%, where in around 82% of world's population is living

[2]. In India, the criteria for blood donor selection and deferral are provided by the Drugs and Cosmetics Act and Rules (1940) and by the Technical Manual issued by the Director General of Health Services (DGHS) [3]. During donor screening, a donor who is disqualified from donating blood is called a deferred donor. Depending on the reason, it could be either a temporary deferral (for a brief period of time) or permanent (will never be allowed to donate blood). The present study was conducted to analyse rate and reasons of donor deferral among blood donors and also to reduce the

number of deferred donors in blood bank so that temporarily deferred donors are identified and counselled to increase the pool of voluntary blood donors without compromising on quality or safety of both donor and recipient [5]. This study can have a direct impact on providing help in planning a more efficient way of selecting donors and curtailing unnecessary deferrals and hence, to build a positive relationship with the donors [6].

Materials and Methods

This study was a retrospective study conducted from 1st January 2022 to 30th November 2024 in the blood centre of a tertiary care teaching hospital. The participants willing for donation were registered and their demographic details were noted. They were given pre - donation counselling, and the medical officer in-charge assessed the following details in them:

1. Evaluated and reviewed their donor questionnaire form
2. Performed brief physical examination of the donor (weight, age, blood pressure, pulse rate, temperature)
3. Performed analysis for donor's haemoglobin levels.

Donors were screened as per the guidelines of the Drug and Cosmetic Act of 1940 (recent amendment in March 2020) and supplemented by guidelines of the DGHS guidelines, Ministry of Health, and Family Welfare (2022)². Those who met the criteria

laid down for donation were accepted for blood donation and those who didn't were deferred from donation while documenting the reasons in the deferral register maintained in the blood bank. Data on all blood donors who were deferred from voluntary blood donation during the study period was included for analysis. Criteria laid down by the NACO guidelines were followed and the following donors were accepted for donation -

1. Individuals aged between 18yrs (completed) and 65 years
2. Donors having weight of 50 kg and above
3. Haemoglobin (Hb) of 12.5 g/dl and above
4. Blood pressure with systolic value ranging between 110 - 140mm/hg and Diastolic value ranging from 70 - 100mm/hg
5. No history of tattooing in the past 6 months.
6. No history of medication intake in the past 72 hours
7. No history of alcohol consumption in the past 24 hours and no history of smoking in the last 6 hours
8. Women not on menstrual cycle on the day of donation
9. No donations were accepted with a history of previous donation less than 3 months ago

The causes of donor deferral were categorized as temporary and permanent, and data was recorded and presented in the form of tables.

Results

Table 1: Age - wise distribution of total deferred donors

Age (in years)	Number of donors	Percentage of deferrals
< 18 years	02	0.58%
18 – 30 years	201	58.43%
31 – 50 years	133	38.66%
Above 50 years	08	2.32%

Table 2: Gender – wise distribution of total deferred donors

Gender	No. of registered donors	No. of deferred donors	Percentage of deferrals
Male	3635	272	7.48%
Female	220	72	32.72%
Total	3855	344	8.89%

Table 3: Distribution of deferred donors by nature of deferral

Nature of deferral	Total	Percentage
Temporary	328	95.34%
Permanent	16	4.62%
Total	344	100%

Table 4: Distribution of causes of temporary deferrals

Reasons for deferral	Number	Percentage
Underweight (<50 kg)	25	7.57%
Giddiness	01	0.303%
Tooth extraction within last 6 months	01	0.303%
H/O donation in the last 3 months	02	0.606%
Low haemoglobin level	71	21.51%
High haemoglobin level	01	0.303%
Low blood pressure level	34	10.30%

High blood pressure level	73	22.12%
Alcohol intake <24 hours before donation	40	12.12%
Tattooing	03	0.909%
Poor venous access	09	2.72%
H/O smoking less than 6 hours before donation	03	0.909%
Kidney stones	03	0.909%
Inadequate sleep	16	4.87%
Menstruation	02	0.606%
Surgery	03	0.909%
Allergy	02	0.606%
Medication Intake	39	11.81%

Table 5: Distribution of causes of permanent deferrals

Reasons for deferral	Number	Percentage
Diagnosed case of TTI's	02	12.5%
Known case of Guillain Barre Syndrome	01	6.25%
Known case of diabetes mellitus on medication	05	31.25%
Known case of hypothyroidism on medication	01	6.25%
History of previous cardiac surgery	03	18.75%
Known case of hypertension on medication	02	12.5%
Known case of epilepsy	02	12.5%

Table 6: Comparison of total deferral rate in our study with similar studies

Name of Study	Total Deferral Rate
Sheetal Malhotra	16%
Basavarajendra	9.74%
Shrivastava	11.5%
Sundar et al	5.8%
Vimal et al	14.87%
Ahmad et al	12.6%
Chauhan et al	5.56%
Iqbal et al	12.9%
Awasthi et al	10.4%
Bobati et al	8.62%
Taneja et al	17.1%
Rabeya et al	5.6%
Lim et al	14.4%
Arundhathi S et al	9.9%
Present study	8.92%

Discussion

In the present study, majority of the donors were males 3363 (92.51 %) compared to female donors who comprised of 148 (8.5%) donors of the total. This finding was similar to studies conducted by Kokani MJ [7] et al, who reported 94.2% male and 5.8% female donors, Unnikrishnan [8] et al who reported 95.13% males and 4.8% female donors.

The reasons could be attributed to male donors having more acceptable range of weight and levels of haemoglobin compared to females. In our study, most of the deferred donors (58.43%), were in the age group of 18-30 years. Similar studies, like Sareen RN [9] et al., reported 60.5%, Arundhathi S [10] et al., reported 57.82% which had comparable results to our study. The reasons for the same can be because of being underweight, having low Hb which

indicates poor nutrition status, tattooing, smoking, alcohol consumption and inadequate sleep which indicate a lack of awareness about blood donation criteria. The deferral rate among females was much higher when compared to males in current study similar to other studies in literature [11,12]. High female deferral rate could be due to increased frequency of anaemia, being underweight, menstruation, lactation, history of pregnancy and abortion, hypothyroidism, cultural habits and lack of motivation to donate blood. In our study, temporary deferrals constituted for about 95.34% and permanent deferrals for 4.62%. This was similar to the study by Jaiswal et al., where temporary and permanent deferrals were accounted for at (96.32%) and (3.68%) respectively [12]. High BP among potential donors was a leading deferral cause in our study with a significant percentage of 22.2%. This was similar to another study by Agnihotri [13] which observed that high blood pressure was a common

cause for deferral in donors. Most of the donors in our study only showed incidental findings of high BP during donor evaluation with no previous diagnosis of hypertension. Other causes for high BP in donors can be due to anxiety in first time donors, fear of phlebotomy, fear of blood and white coat hypertension. This was followed by donors having low haemoglobin as another leading cause for temporary deferral with 21.51%. Like our study, most other studies done have also shown low haemoglobin as the main reason for deferral of blood donors [15,16]. This indicates a high prevalence of anaemia (particularly the iron deficiency type) in the population. Anaemia in females is more likely to be related to physiological causes like menstruation, pregnancies, lactation, or nutritional deficiencies. However, anaemia in male donors may relate to nutritional deficiencies or underlying medical reasons. The most common cause for permanent deferral in our study was donors diagnosed with diabetes on medication which accounted for 31.25%. This was near to the results of the study by Papatnam K et al [16] (20.91%) in contrary to the other studies which mentioned hypertension as the commonest cause. Our deferral rate was similar (8.92%) to study conducted by Basavarajegowda A [17], where the deferral rate was 9.7% [22], Panchbhaiyya MM et al [4] was 11.9%, Awasthi S et al [19] showing a deferral rate of 10.4% which is in comparison with our study.

Limitations of the Study

1. The present study was conducted in a selected blood centre. Drawing any generalized ideas from this study, therefore, cannot depict an idea about the actual scenario.
2. Duration of this study was only 2 years 10 months with a relatively small sample size. More extensive study over longer duration with a larger sample size can give better insight.
3. This was a retrospective study. In case of prospective study, it helps to follow - up donors who were deferred to find out if donors with temporary deferral can be encouraged for successful blood donation once the deferral period is over.

Conclusion

This study helps in refining our donor screening methods and donor criteria which will provide efficient blood transfusion services and create a safe pool of blood donors to the blood centre. Current findings also suggest the need to educate and create awareness among the general public about the practices that can be avoided before blood donation. Our study showed that the majority of donor deferrals were due to temporary causes. So, donors need to be properly evaluated before blood donation and counselled to come back for donation after the temporary deferral period is over. Defining and

educating the donor selection criteria to the community are the key factors to achieve a higher acceptance of blood donors.

References

1. Pai S, East Point College of Medical Sciences, Chabba SK, East Point College of Medical Sciences. An evaluation of donor deferrals in A blood bank of a tertiary care hospital A 3½-year study. *Ann Pathol Lab Med [Internet]*. 2020;7(3): A126-131.
2. Patil O, Jayaprakash CS. Evaluation of Causes of Deferral among Blood Donors. *J Hematol Transfus*. 2021;8(1).
3. Malhotra S, Negi G. Analysis of reasons of blood donor deferral at a tertiary care institute in India and its reflections on community health status. *Asian J Transfus Sci [Internet]*. 2023;17(1):48–52.
4. Panchbhaiya M M, Patel J P, Visavadiya R S. Evaluation of Blood Donor Selection and Deferrals in a Tertiary Care Hospital Blood Centre. *Annals of pathology and lab medicine [Internet]*. 2024 Nov 7;11(7):A-141-A 147.
5. Priya ES. Retrospective analysis of patterns of donor deferral among blood donors in a tertiary care hospital. *Int J Contemp Med Res [IJCMR] [Internet]*. 2019;6(1).
6. Patil S B, C N Anushree, P N Neeta, R Sujata. Blood donor deferrals in a tertiary care teaching hospital blood bank in Bangalore - A retrospective study. *Blood donor deferrals in a tertiary care teaching hospital blood bank in Bangalore - A retrospective study [Internet]*. 4(1):135–8.
7. Kokani MJ, Menapara CB. Evaluation of different criteria for blood donor deferral in a hospital affiliated with teaching institute. *Trop J Path Micro*. 2019;5(4):227–32.
8. Unnikrishnan B, Rao P, Kumar N, Ganti S, Prasad R, Amarnath A, et al. Profile of blood donors and reasons for deferral in coastal South India. *Australas Med J [Internet]*. 2011; 4(7):379–85.
9. Rajendra DN, Department of Pathology, Dr. B R Ambedkar Medical College and Research Centre, KG Halli, Bangalore, Karnataka, India, Madapura DP V, Department of Paediatrics, M.S Ramaiah Medical College and Hospital, MSRIT Post, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. Study of blood donor profile in a blood bank attached to a medical college hospital - a retrospective study. *Trop J Pathol Microbiol [Internet]*. 2017;3(4):406–11.
10. Arundhathi S, Shanthi JK. A two-year retrospective cross-sectional study of donor deferrals in voluntary blood donation camps in a tertiary trauma and orthopaedic centre. *Trop J Pathol Microbiol*. 2019; 5:150–5.
11. Chauhan DN, Desai KN, Trivedi HJ, Agnihotri A, Patel S, Patel J, et al. The Study of deferred

- blood donors at tertiary level hospital-based blood bank of South Gujarat. *J evolution Medic dental Sci*. 2015; 4:4590–8
12. Jaiswal M, Maheshwari S, Saxena R, Yadav P. Analysis of pre-donation deferral causes in blood donors at a rural medical institute of ro-hilkhand region, India. *Int J Biomed Adv Res* [Internet]. 2016;7(3):113. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7439/ijbar.v7i3.3060>
 13. Agnihotri N. Whole blood donor deferral analysis at a center in Western India. *Asian J Transfus Sci* [Internet]. 2010;4(2):116–22.
 14. Bahadur S, Jain S, Goel RK, Pahuja S, Jain M. Analysis of blood donor deferral characteristics in Delhi, India. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health*. 2009;40(5):1087–91.
 15. Rabeya Y, Rapiaah M, Rosline H, Ahmed SA, Zaidah WA, Roshan TM. Blood pre-donation deferrals--a teaching hospital experience. *Southeast Asian J Trop Med Public Health*. 2008;39(3):571–4.
 16. Paparatnam K, Rajani K. An evaluation of blood donor deferral causes at tertiary care centre of srikakulam district. *J Evol Med Dent Sci* [Internet]. 2016;5(26):1349–51
 17. Basavarajegowda A. Whole blood donor deferral causes in a tertiary care teaching hospital blood bank from south India. *Hematol Transfus Int J* [Internet]. 2017;5(2)
 18. Zachariah A A, Sabu R, Thomas B M. Proportion of blood donor deferral and its associated causes- a cross-sectional study in a tertiary care centre. *International Journal of Academic Medicine and Pharmacy* [Internet]. :871–4.
 19. Awasthi S, Dutta S, Haritwal A, Ansari M, Arathi N, Agarwal D. Evaluation of the reasons for predonation deferral of prospective blood donors in a tertiary teaching hospital in North India. *The Internet J Public Health TM*. 2009;2155–6733.